

D3.1 – Production and delivery of polyols

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Index

Executive Summary.....	4
Introduction	5
Introduction and Objectives of NewWave.....	5
Thermo-Chemical Fractionation & sugar hydrogenation	6
Production of polyol samples	7
Results.....	7
Polyol samples prepared and shipped to AEP	7
Analysis of polyols samples.....	9
Conclusions	9

List of figures

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the NewWave ML's.....	5
Figure 2: On left TCF pilot plant, on the right HDO pilot plant	6
Figure 3: Examples of polyol samples	8

List of tables

Table 1: Polyol samples prepared and shipped to AEP	8
Table 2. Analysis of samples prepared.....	9

Executive Summary

D3.1 is the first of three deliverables describing the production and delivery of polyol samples. These deliverables are part of sub-task 3.1: Production of polyols (M1-M36). This document describes the first polyol samples produced and delivered to the relevant project partners in the period M1-M12. The polyols were produced at BTG, by the hydrogenation of pyrolysis oil or the pyrolytic sugars. The hydrogenation was executed in bench-scale or pilot-scale hydrotreaters applying the patented Ni-based PICULA™ catalyst. After hydrogenation of the feed, different post-treatments/purification steps were applied to remove impurities. The eight polyol samples produced were sent to partner AEP to be tested in different polyurethane applications.

Introduction

Introduction and Objectives of NewWave

NewWave will contribute to building a circular economy by introducing sustainable raw materials in different manufacturing lines (ML's), replacing toxic chemicals, and lowering the environmental footprint of the products. The four manufacturing lines (see Figure 1) will produce engineered wood panels, furan base-chemicals, polyols and polyurethanes, and modified/engineered wood. These lines are not chosen 'at random', rather they evolved from previous research and technology development work and will reach TRL-6 by the end of the project. The products produced in the manufacturing lines will be used to enhance the sustainability of building materials in the construction industry. NewWave aims at wood-based materials including Cross Laminated Timber (CLT) to replace steel and concrete as structural components, modified/engineered wood to replace tropical hardwood or chemically treated wood for outdoor use, and Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) and plywood for interior usage. Toxic chemicals like formaldehyde and creosote will be replaced by non-toxic, bio-based alternatives. Within the project, a small demonstration project will be built with these materials to show the products and test their durability.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the NewWave ML's

Thermo-Chemical Fractionation & sugar hydrogenation

The sustainable raw materials used in the manufacturing lines are obtained by Thermo-Chemical Fractionation (TCF) of biomass residues and end-of-life products. TCF is an innovative, two-step conversion process to transform different bio-resources into sustainable raw materials and is currently at a TRL-6/7. In the TCF process biomass is first converted by fast pyrolysis into Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil (FPBO). Subsequently, the FPBO is fractionated -based on chemical functionality- yielding a reactive lignin fraction and a sugar-rich fraction, both being excellent starting materials to produce sustainable, bio-based chemicals & materials. The selected product lines fully exploit the unique chemical functionalities already present in the biomass feeds. Moreover, the lines are interlinked, and output from one line will further improve the sustainability of the other. Wastewater treatment and water re-use is integral part of the NewWave concept. Combined with end-of-life recycling options and efficient use of byproducts this results in essentially waste-free manufacturing processes.

Figure 2: On left TCF pilot plant, on the right HDO pilot plant

FPBO, and the pyrolytic sugar fraction can be used as a raw material for the production of green polyols. In TCF, the pyrolytic sugars (PS) are obtained as a watery solution that can directly be processed in hydrogenation. Furthermore, the pyrolytic lignin fraction can be used in other added value applications such as various resin systems, minimalizing the production of waste residues. At BTG, the TCF process is performed on pilot-scale (see Figure 2). The pyrolytic sugar

fraction consists of small sugar derived molecules such as glycoaldehyde, levoglucosan, cellobiosan, large polymer fractions of cellulose but also other organic components such as carboxylic acids and lignin derived phenolics etc. At BTG, the production of pyrolysis oil derived polyols is conducted on bench- & pilot-scale (see Figure 2).

Production of polyol samples

The polyols are produced at BTG by the hydrogenation of fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) or the pyrolytic sugars (PS). The hydrogenation is executed in bench-scale or pilot-scale hydrotreaters applying the patented Ni-based PICULA™ catalyst. In addition, also alternative inhouse prepared catalysts will be tested at various process conditions in an endeavor to increase the yield of small polyols. After hydrogenation of the feed, post-treated and/or further purification will be applied to make the polyols suitable to be used as a green additive or as raw materials for the production of polyurethanes. The mixed polyols, the MEG (mono ethylene glycol) and MPG (mono propylene glycol) will be used by AEP as the starting polyols or as chain extenders in polyurethane production and as an additive in the manufacturing of formulations to modify wood by BTG.

Results

Polyol samples prepared and shipped to AEP

A large amount of SPO (stabilized pyrolysis oil) was produced by the hydrogenation of FPBO applying the PICULA™ catalyst under elevated but standard T and PH₂. A smaller amount of SPS (stabilized pyrolytic sugars) was produced by the hydrogenation of PS under similar conditions in a bench-scale hydrotreater. Both The SPO and SPS contain a large fraction of polyols and were subsequently post-treated to remove impurities such as residual lignin. An overview of the samples produced and sent to AEP for testing in PUR-systems is given in Table 1. Figure 3, shows a photo of some of the samples produced. The samples produced contain both the large and smaller polyols (mixed), only the small (monomeric) polyols, or only the large (oligomeric & polymeric) polyols.

Table 1: Polyol samples prepared and shipped to AEP

Sample no.	Sample name	Sample description ¹	Internal BTG code	Shipment code	Amount (g)	Shipment date
1	BTG_NW_SPOF	Mixed polyols derived from SPO	BTG-2395	2022-2567	300 g	24/05/22
2	BTG_NW_SPOL	Light polyols derived from SPO	BTG-2479	2022-2566	300 g	24/05/22
3	BTG_NW_SPOH	Heavy polyols derived from SPO	BTG-2410	2022-2565	800 g	24/05/22
4	BTG_NW_SPSL	Light polyols derived from SPS	BTG-2494	2022-2619	90 ml	16/11/22
5	BTG_NW_SPSH	Heavy polyols derived from SPS	BTG-2427	2022-2621	350 ml	16/11/22
6	BTG_NW_SPSL	Light polyols derived from SPS	BTG-2493	2022-2618	50 ml	16/11/22
7	BTG_NW_SPOFE	Extracted mixed polyols derived from SPO	BTG-2892	2022-2620	175 ml	16/11/22
8	BTG_NW_SPOLE	Extracted light polyols derived from SPO	BTG-2954	2022-2622	50 ml	16/11/22

¹: SPO: Stabilized pyrolysis oil, ²: Stabilized pyrolytic sugars

Figure 3: Examples of polyol samples

Analysis of polyols samples

For all samples, standard analysis was performed including HPLC-analysis (if possible) to determine the small polyol content. Results of these analysis are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Analysis of samples prepared.

	2022-2565	2022-2566	2022-2567	2022-2618	2022-2619	2022-2620	2022-2621	2022-2622
	BTG-2410	BTG-2479	BTG-2395	BTG-2493	BTG-2494	BTG-2892	BTG-2427	BTG-2954
HPLC¹								
MEG (wt%)	ND	35,6	21,9	26,9	35,2	28,8	- ²	35,0
MPG (wt%)	ND	15,9	11,3	10,3	14,7	12,5	- ²	14,2
Standard analysis								
C/H/N (wt%)	63,1/7,8/,0,0	49,0/9,6/0,0	49,0/9,3/0,0	51,5/9,4/0,2	50,0/9,1/0,1	46,2/8,7/0,0	58,4/6,8/0,5	48,3/9,8/0,0
Karl Fischer H ₂ O (wt%)	0,6	1,0	2,1	1,7	1,9	2,5	0,5	1,1
TAN (mg KOH/g) ³	11,6	40,7	37,1	61,4	64,6	15,2	11,5	12,6
CAN (mmol/g) ⁴	- ²	0,2	2,6	1,7	1,9	0,5	2,4	0,0
pH	4,5	4,4	4,0	4,2	4,3	3,8	4,6	4,4
CR (wt%) ⁵	15,6	0,0	3,9	1,1	0,6	3,2	25,4	0,0

¹: HPLC analysis: MEG = Mono ethylene glycol, MPG = Mono propylene glycol. ²: could not be determined by HPLC. ³: Total acid number. ⁴: Carbonyl number. ⁵: Carbon residue.

Conclusions

D3.1 is the first of three deliverables on the production and delivery of polyol samples to partner AEP. The polyols were produced at BTG, by the hydrogenation of pyrolysis oil or the pyrolytic sugars. The hydrogenation was executed in bench-scale or pilot-scale hydrotreaters applying the patented Ni-based PICULA™ catalyst. After hydrogenation of the feed, different post-treatments/purification steps were applied to remove impurities. The eight polyol samples produced were analyzed and sent to partner AEP to be tested in different polyurethane applications.

The logo consists of two stylized, overlapping wave shapes in a golden-brown color, positioned to the left of the text.

NewWave

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